

ISic0625

I.Sicily inscription 0625

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone (white, from Trapani)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

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Autopsy

Metcalfe

2015.11.12

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo archeologico regionale Lilibeo Marsala - Baglio Anselmi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR074417

1. C (aio) Mevio Q (uinti) f (ilio) Donato
2. Iuniano q (uaestori) pro pr (aetore)
3. provinc (iae) Siciliae
4. optimo et humaniss (imo)
5. XII trib (us) patrono

Apparatus

Text via EDR

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175812

EDR 074417

EDCS 12800325

Bibliography

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Calderone, S. 1959. Lilybaeum. In De Ruggerio, E.(eds.), *Dizionario Epigrafico di Antichità romane*. Rome. pp. 1069-1072. At 1071-1072

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